

D3.3 Final report on policies and strategies

Version Final

Date 13th of December 2022

Grant Agreement number: 823914

Project acronym: ARIADNEplus

Project title: Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe - plus

Funding Scheme: H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1

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The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Horizon 2020 Programme (H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1) under grant agreement n° 823914.

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Document History

- 16.11.2022 – Draft Version 0.1
- 20.11.2022 - Review 0.2
- 04.12.2022 - Review 0.3
- 09.12.2022 - Review 0.4
- 13.12.2022 - Final Version

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1 Executive Summary

1.1 ARIADNEplus objectives

As a follow up on the initial ARIADNE project, the overall objective of ARIADNEplus is to serve archaeological researchers and data management communities by proceeding to improve data sharing and the (re)use of data resources, which are dispersed throughout Europe and often difficult to discover and access as different silos (institutional, national or disciplinary).

1.2 Policies and Good Practices for FAIR Archaeological Data Management

This final report is the third and final deliverable of Work Package 3. It builds on the first report D3.1, in which the outcomes of the initial ARIADNE project as well as the PARTHENOS project, which were used as starting points for the current ARIADNEplus project, were taken into account [Hollander 2020]. It also builds on the second, interim report D3.2, in which the activities of the partners to support the creation of FAIR data in the archaeological sector were described [Hollander 2022]. This current report summarises the activities carried out by the different partners during the four-year project duration (January 2019 – December 2022), as well as the results achieved through the work package. The following partners have been involved: DANS-KNAW, PIN, UoY-ADS, CNR, CONICET, BUP, NIAM-BAS, AMZ, ARUP, AU, UH, CNRS, INRAP, RGK, ATHENA-RC, PP, HNM, FI, IAA, MIBACT-ICCU, NARA, DGCP, SND, and ASU.

The objectives of Work Package 3 “Policies and Good Practices for FAIR Data Management” are to:

- Support the creation of FAIR data in the archaeological sector.
- Define and spread guidelines to good practices in archaeological data management.
- Adapt standard quality criteria for datasets and data to the archaeological case, and support their implementation among users.

Chapter 2 describes how to define and disseminate guidelines on good practices in archaeological data management. Commonly developed and widely applicable guides ensure that archaeological data will be FAIR and available in the long-term.

Chapter 3 presents an overview of the activities to develop and implement a portfolio of tools to support users in their work with archaeological data. The ARIADNEplus partners developed and implemented a new Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template for Archaeological Datasets, a Protocol for Archaeological Data Management, and a Guide for Archaeological Data Management Planning, accessible through the new ARIADNEplus DMP tool.¹ The Policy Wizard Tool was updated.

Chapter 4 shows the importance of sharing experiences from partners with already certified repositories to partners willing to set up an archaeological data repository. Providing guidelines and support on repository creation and management was the focus of activity here. Workshops, webinars, symposia and hackathons took place and scientific articles on data management policies and practices of digital archaeological repositories were published.

Chapter 5 describes what partners willing to certify their repository need to be provided with: the explanation of and training on accreditation requirements when applied to repositories of archaeological data with a perspective on international initiatives, e.g. access restrictions for security

¹ <https://vast-lab.org/dmp/index.html>

and privacy reasons. Achieving a Trustworthy Digital Repository status, and making and keeping data FAIR is a joint journey.

Chapter 6 highlights the application of the FAIR principles to archaeological data, taking into account different regulations throughout Europe and the potential sensitivities and IPR-related issues. The aim is to work towards solutions that harmonise the diverse approaches adopted. A major step forward has been an online survey conducted among repositories, with 60 respondents, giving essential insights into current policies and where there is room for improvement.

Chapter 7 describes training activities on FAIR data management. Training and training materials have been produced and published.

2 Good practices in archaeological data management

Task 3.1 built on the work of the first phase of the ARIADNE project under WP4 “Good Practices and Dissemination”, and specifically on Task 4.5 “Good Practices” and Task 4.6 “Guides to Good Practice”. UoY-ADS led the task, with SND, MIBACT-ICCU, and DGPC.

2.1 Good practice documents

The initial survey of ARIADNE partner organisations, carried out as Task 4.5 in the first phase of the ARIADNE project, highlighted the existence of a variety of guidelines and Good Practice documents. These documents reflected a broad range of expertise and function while also highlighting several specific themes which formed the objectives for work carried out under Task 4.6 “Guides to Good Practice” [Niven 2016]. The objectives included:

- The alignment and referencing of existing Good Practice documents.
- The creation of case studies illustrating the application of Good Practice documents to specific data sets for which no good practice existed previously.
- The incorporation of guidelines produced by the ArchaeoLandscapes and 3D-ICONS projects into ARIADNE guidelines, and the illustration of these guidelines through relevant case studies.
- The revision, creation, or enhancement of guidelines for 3D datasets.
- The creation of guidelines for data from scientific dating and analysis, specifically dendrochronological datasets.

Tasks 4.5 and 4.6 successfully met these objectives, and produced several new and much-needed guidelines, available via the ARIADNEplus Training Hub,² which links to the Archaeology Data Service.³ The guides and case studies successfully incorporated existing material and guidelines from a wide range of sources, ranging from the outputs of other collaborative projects such as 3D-ICONS through to organisation-specific guidelines produced by project partners such as DAI and DANS. DANS, in particular, worked to develop resources around the FAIR principles, for example within the PARTHENOS project, allowing ARIADNEplus to incorporate these important principles into Good Practice work right away.⁴ Outcomes from within ARIADNEplus were also integrated, such as the 2019 user survey presented in D2.1 *Initial Report on Community Needs* [Geser 2019]. Additionally, case studies were used both within individual guides and as stand-alone contributions to successfully illustrate the application of data selection, archiving, and documentation procedures to real-world datasets.

When viewed together, the outputs highlighted that, while language, procedure, and archaeological practices may vary widely between countries and institutions, the data that arises from archaeological investigations and projects, irrespective of geography, share common elements that allow guides for good practice to be commonly developed and widely applicable.

2.2 ARIADNE/ARIADNEplus representation and results in other projects

At the completion of the preparatory phase for the European Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS), as the partner representing ARIADNEplus and archaeology more broadly within E-RIHS, the

² <http://training.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/managing-datasets-from-large-archaeological-projects/>

³ <https://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/GuideAim>

⁴ http://www.PARTHENOS-project.eu/portal/policies_guidelines

Archaeology Data Service undertook discussions as to whether to pursue another Guide to Good Practice for Archaeological Science Data. Based on the lessons learned from participation in E-RIHS, this was deemed impractical. This area of archaeological research was deemed so complex and diverse, that any single guide would not be of practical use. Instead, work continued within ARIADNEplus in trying to better understand the archaeological science data landscape, so that it will be possible to create guidance in the future.

Over the last year, the Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project was also completed. SSHOC included 20 partner organisations and their 27 associates to develop the social sciences and humanities area of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).⁵ The Archaeology Data Service represented ARIADNEplus and archaeology more generally within the consortium. The examination of the issues and challenges faced in providing FAIR access to archaeological data was completed, resulting in a comprehensive deliverable *Report on opening access to research data in the archaeology domain* [Wright et al. 2022]. In addition to including the previously envisioned internal and external audit of the FAIRness of archaeological data held by the ADS, an additional collaboration was undertaken with the FAIRsFAIR project to test the machine actionability of ADS data using the F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool [Devaraju et al. 2022]. The comprehensive international survey of repository practices undertaken within ARIADNEplus [Geser et al, 2022], discussed extensively in [section 6](#), was also analysed within the SSHOC deliverable to better understand FAIR implementation for archaeological data in Europe.

In addition to informing the SSHOC/EOSC community about the FAIRness of archaeological data based on the work undertaken by ARIADNEplus, the work done within SSHOC has been fed back, to the ARIADNE metadata providers through their participation in activities led by the COST Action Saving European Archaeology from the Digital Dark Age (SEADDA CA18128) and through participation in the ARIADNEplus Transnational Access activities run by ADS within the ARIADNE Data Stewardship Winter School in November/December 2022.

2.3 Harmonised guidance for Protocol and Data Management Plan Templates

Science Europe, the European association representing the interests of major public research performing and research funding organisations, published two documents with great relevance for Task 3.1 on good practices in archaeological data management. The 2018 guidance document “Presenting a Framework for Discipline-specific Research Data Management” proposed the creation of domain-specific protocols to be used as standardised templates for RDM, reducing the administrative burden on both researchers and research organisations, as well as on funders.⁶

First in 2019, and then updated and extended in 2021, the “Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management” was prepared by experts from Science Europe member organisations.⁷ The guide aims to align RDM core requirements across research and funding organisations, with the 2021 extension adding an Evaluation Rubric, providing guidance for evaluators of Data Management Plans (DMPs) on what are considered to be necessary or acceptable answers. Many research councils and universities in Europe, including the Horizon Europe programme, accept

⁵ <https://sshopencloud.eu/>

⁶ Science Europe (2018). Guidance Document Presenting a Framework for Discipline-specific Research Data Management. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4925907>.

⁷ Science Europe (2021). Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management - Extended Edition. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915862>; See also Science Europe (2021). Q&A: Aligning Research Data Management Across Europe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4923141>.

the Science Europe core requirements as the basis for a DMP in order to make research open and FAIR. A close collaboration between Science Europe and ARIADNEplus took place, with DANS and PIN in charge of the work.

It was expected that Horizon Europe requirements of the European Commission would follow the Science Europe core requirements, but when they were published while the ARIADNEplus work was in progress, it appeared that they were largely a continuation of the Horizon 2020 requirements, with a number of modifications. Although Horizon Europe and Science Europe have similar DMP aims and topics, they differ substantially in detail. The structure and the order of the questions to be covered, as well as many textual formulations are quite different, as is the emphasis on topics and the way in which these are grouped. As part of the ARIADNEplus project, we made a mapping to provide clarity on both the similarities and dissimilarities.⁸ As a consequence it was impossible to use the same setup for the DMP Protocol and Template.

In the ARIADNEplus project, a Domain Data Protocol for Archaeology, compliant with the Core DMP requirements by Science Europe, was developed as a complement to the already existing DMP Template for archaeological research data management (see section 3). In the first 18 months of the project, the activities focused on the definition of the guidance, incorporating the PARTHENOS Guidelines on how to make data FAIR and the guidance drafted in collaboration with OpenAIRE. The work carried out by the working group formed by Peter Doorn (DANS) and Paola Ronzino (PIN) during month 19-48 continued with the refinement of the ARIADNEplus DMP Template's guidance and on the harmonisation with the core requirements formulated by Science Europe, and checking the Protocol against the Science Europe Evaluation Rubric for DMPs. The working group incorporated the Domain Protocol idea by proposing norms for good practices in data management for use by the archaeological community. The resulting Protocol provides extensive guidance, with explanations of and references to relevant information resources concerning archaeological data management.⁹ The guidance document follows the order of the Science Europe core requirements, and it is possible to link back and forth between the guidance, Templates, and Protocol. This guidance document obviously makes use of previously existing guidelines and good practices, but it is exactly the tailoring to the individual items of the Protocol and DMP Templates that sets it apart from other guides. The full guidance document is available in the training hub of the ARIADNEplus website as a document of about 20 pages and as an online tool, described in the next section.

⁸ Mapping between H2020-HE-SE: <https://tinyurl.com/2p8j77r4>

⁹ <https://training.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/dmp-guidance/>

3 ARIADNEplus policy support tools

Task 3.2 has implemented a portfolio of tools created to support users in their work with archaeological data. DANS-KNAW leads the task, supported by PIN, MIBACT-ICCU, DGPC and other partners as required.

One of the objectives of this task is the release of a tool that enables the archaeological community to comply with the requirements of funding institutions, who often request the submission of a data management plan (DMP) to document that they manage their data responsibly during the research process. Three DMP tools¹⁰ and one policy wizard tool were developed. The ARIADNEplus DMP tools link to the aforementioned Guide for Archaeological Data Management Planning¹¹ and facilitate the compilation of:

- The ARIADNEplus DMP Researcher Template for Archaeological Datasets, based on Horizon 2020 requirements, and mapped to the ARGOS tool.¹² While the tool is new, the Template was initially developed in the PARTHENOS project.¹³
- The Horizon Europe DMP Template for Archaeological Datasets.¹⁴ This is a new template based on the RDM requirements of Horizon Europe, newly developed by the ARIADNEplus project.
- The Domain Protocol for Archaeological Data Management, also newly developed by ARIADNEplus. It is based on Science Europe Core Requirements and Evaluation Rubric.¹⁵

The Guide for Archaeological Data Management Planning is harmonised between the three and can be consulted for both DMP templates and the Protocol (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Links between the ARIADNEplus data management tools and guidance.

A certain divergence among the DMP Templates and the Protocol was unavoidable, because of the differences between the Horizon Europe and Science Europe requirements. Archaeologists have a

¹⁰ <https://vast-lab.org/dmp/index.html>

¹¹ <https://training.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/dmp-guidance/>

¹² <https://vast-lab.org/dmp/ariadneplus/form/index.html>

¹³ <https://www.parthenos-project.eu/portal/dmp>

¹⁴ <https://vast-lab.org/dmp/horizoneurope/form/index.html>

¹⁵ <https://vast-lab.org/dmp/dataprotocol/form/index.html>

choice of approaches and online modules to comply with the requirements of either Horizon Europe or Science Europe.

3.1 General introduction to the Templates

The DMP Templates and the Protocol are all based on the Open Science initiative and the FAIR principles.¹⁶ They specifically address researchers in the archaeological domain and are tailored to community needs, including standards and tools commonly used in archaeological practice. The templates satisfy the needs of research organisations that manage institutional repositories, with sections/questions tailored to them, and of researchers, as they are both the data producers and data users.

With its structure, related guidance, and suggested answers, the templates help researchers think about what to do with their research data, how to collect and keep track of it, thus helping to identify the support, standards, and services needed. They make researchers aware of the options for short- and long-term storage, and to prepare data for re-use by acknowledging the sources and intellectual contributions according to legal terms and conditions that may include limited privileged use.

The need for support in the compilation of a DMP was strongly expressed by a group of experts that responded to a survey carried out by the Research Data Management team of the OpenAIRE project and the FAIR Data Expert Group to collect feedback for the evaluation of the Horizon2020 approach to DMPs in order to identify gaps and collect suggestions for improvement [Grootveld et al. 2018]. This need has been further confirmed by the extended community of ARIADNEplus and by the archaeologists and experts of the archaeological domain that are part of the SEADDA community, to which we submitted the ARIADNEplus DMP Researcher Template and the tool, asking for their comments and validation.

3.2 The ARIADNEplus DMP Researcher Template for Archaeological Datasets

The ARIADNEplus DMP Researcher Template for Archaeological Datasets was originally developed by the PARTHENOS project and follows the same structure as the Horizon 2020 Guidelines (Fig. 2). It is compliant with the guidelines on FAIR Data Management published by the European Commission to ensure that research is publicly available, to help Horizon 2020 beneficiaries in making their research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, with the main objective of increasing the scientific quality of the funded projects. It consists of a set of questions organised in the following sections:

¹⁶ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

1. Data Summary (e.g. data set description)
2. FAIR Data
 - 2.1. Making data Findable, including provisions for metadata (e.g. persistent identifier, naming conventions, metadata standards)
 - 2.2. Making data openly accessible (e.g. repository)
 - 2.3. Making data interoperable (e.g. vocabularies)
 - 2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)
3. Allocation of resources
4. Data security
5. Ethical aspects
6. Other

All the sections include questions aimed at researchers, while section 4 on “Data Security” mostly addressed data managers and repository managers, as it concerns information on data recovery, as well as secure storage of sensitive data, details which a researcher is not necessarily informed about.

DMP Researcher Template for Archaeological Datasets v.1.0

Load
Save

Step 1

Step 2

Step 3

Step 4

Step 5

Step 6

Step 7

Step 8

Step 9

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

2.4.1 Specify how the data will be licensed to permit the widest reuse possible
[Guidance](#)

Data will be public domain (e.g. Creative Commons CC0 dedication or CC-BY license)
 Standard reuse license will be used
 Other

Here you can explain your choice

2.4.2 Specify when the data will be made available for reuse
[Guidance](#)

Reuse is subordinated to legitimate interests of rights holders and protection of confidentiality and personal information
 Embargo date can only be handled when the technical framework allows it
 Date individually set with repository
 No specific date
 Other

Here you can explain your choice

Figure 2. Screenshot of part of the DMP Researcher Template for Archaeological Datasets online tool.

The group responsible for this activity collaborated with a team from the OpenAIRE project, and integrated the ARIADNEplus DMP Template into the ARGOS tool.¹⁷ ARGOS is an open extensible service that simplifies the management, validation, monitoring and maintenance of DMPS. It allows researchers, managers, supervisors, etc. to create actionable DMPs that may be freely exchanged among infrastructures for carrying out specific aspects of the data management process in accordance with the intentions and commitment of the data owners. The ARIADNEplus DMP Template has been tested and embedded into the ARGOS environment. This guarantees greater visibility and to reach a larger community. A mapping of the ARIADNEplus DMP Template with the RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable Data Management Plans has been carried out to allow integration into the ARGOS environment. On the other side, ARIADNEplus contributed to the ARGOS multidisciplinary aspect by sharing standards, vocabularies and other information specific to the archaeological domain.

3.3 The Domain Protocol for Archaeological Data Management

This is called the Archaeology Data Protocol in the online tool.¹⁸ As part of task 3.2, a Domain Data Protocol for Archaeology, compliant with the Science Europe Core DMP requirements, was developed as a complement to the already existing Horizon 2020-based DMP Template for archaeological research data management.

The Protocol offers pre-formulated statements and replies to the topics raised and questions asked in the Science Europe Core RDM requirements and also incorporates the suggestions of the Evaluation Rubric. The design of the Protocol is tailored to the fields of archaeology and heritage studies and is based on the principle of “comply or explain” (Fig. 3). Researchers complying with the statements in the Protocol can save a lot of time when preparing a DMP, since a motivation is only required when deviating from the standard reply. Where relevant, it is also possible to provide extra information on the standard answers of the Protocol in free text boxes, which can be filled out with optional further explanations.

¹⁷ <https://argos.openaire.eu>

¹⁸ <https://vast-lab.org/dmp/dataprotocol/form/index.html>

Archaeology Data Protocol v.1.0

Step 1
Step 2
Step 3
Step 4
Step 5
Step 6

1. Data description and collection or reuse of existing data

1.a. How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be reused?

1a.1. The research team has checked whether previous data on the subject of the research exist that can be reused. If this is the case, such data will be reused, respecting licenses and applicable constraints, including intellectual property rights.

[Guidance](#)

- Comply
 Not applicable (no reusable data exist)

In case of non-compliance:

State the reasons why re-use of existing data has been considered but was discarded.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the first item of the Archaeology Data Protocol in the online tool.

The Protocol consists of a set of statements, organised in the following sections (directly derived from the Science Europe core requirements):

1. Data descriptions and collection or reuse of existing data;
2. Documentation and data quality;
3. Storage and backup during the research process;
4. Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct;
5. Data sharing and long-term preservation;
6. Data management responsibilities and resources.

3.4 The Horizon Europe DMP Template for Archaeological Datasets

As mentioned above, because of diverging RDM requirements of Horizon 2020, Science Europe and Horizon Europe, ARIADNEplus developed an additional DMP Template based on the Horizon Europe 2021-2027 programme RDM requirements. It consists of a set of questions organised in the following sections:

1. Data Summary
2. FAIR Data
 - a. Making data Findable, including provisions for metadata
 - b. Making data accessible
 - i. Repository
 - ii. Data
 - iii. Metadata
 - c. Making data interoperable
 - d. Increase data re-use
3. Other research outputs
4. Allocation of resources
5. Data security
6. Ethics
7. Other issues

Like the other templates, the Horizon Europe DMP Template for Archaeological Datasets is tailored specifically to archaeology and cultural heritage, by providing answer categories which are relevant for this domain (Fig. 4).

Thesauri and vocabularies:

Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)

PeriodO

Pleiades

National vocabularies

Ad hoc/proprietary vocabularies

Other

Here you can explain your choice

Figure 4. Suggested answers for one of the Template questions, tailored to archaeology.

3.5 The ARIADNEplus DMP tool

The online tool consists of three modules that can be selected from the homepage, based on the user's needs (Fig. 5). Once the relevant template is selected, the user is directed to the pertinent page and guided to fill in the questions by following the links to the relevant sections of the online guidance document. A downloadable template for each module is available for consultation before entering information or to use without the online tool.

The online interface has been designed to facilitate the compilation of the DMP through the use of intuitive and user-friendly solutions. The questions that the researcher is invited to answer are divided into successive pages, enriched by a common progress bar that presents itself as the main reference point for the user. The overall view of the various parts that make up the model guides the user step by step, indicating approximately the time required to complete them.

Figure 5. Homepage of the ARIADNEplus online DMP and Protocol tools.

Each page groups similar thematic questions, divided into mandatory and optional, enriched by informative pop-ups that help the user fill them in. If some of the points deemed mandatory for submitting the DMP have not been completed, their number will be displayed in red in the progress bar. At the end of the compilation procedure, it is possible to download the information the DMP contains in PDF format, and in JSON. The JSON file is essential within the application, as it offers the user the opportunity to save a version of the work. In fact, the compilation of the questionnaire can be interrupted at any time by downloading the JSON file containing the current data. This file can be reloaded within the online interface to continue and finish the job. If instead, the compilation of the questionnaire is definitive, the data contained in the file will constitute a version of the DMP useful for any subsequent revisions or updates. None of the user's personal data are collected or stored.

Each Template can be completed independently and saved as a single document. Nevertheless, since the level of detail of each Template is different, for example from a more general view of the Domain Protocol to the more detailed analysis of the ARIADNEplus DMP, interlinks have been created between the Templates to learn more on a specific topic.

A machine-readable DMP was created, which is at the same time interoperable, editable and shareable within the community of stakeholders. The design of future application developments is aimed at making the data contained within the DMPs shareable and interoperable between those research communities that will adopt common solutions to facilitate cooperation between their systems. Making documents interoperable means making sure that the information they contain can be exchanged between different systems in a complete and reliable way. For this it is necessary to consider both the syntactic and the semantic aspects of the data. Computers can process and manage most of the information syntactically, if it is encoded in standard formats such as XML or JSON, but they are unable to interpret and "understand" it if it is not modelled using controlled vocabularies and standards. The DMPs that can be generated with the current version of the tool already meet the requirements for syntactic interoperability, thanks to the encoding in JSON format.

The ARIADNEplus DMP tool assists researchers in generating their DMP by means of user-friendly interfaces intended to simplify the work of input, control data and monitor the descriptive process. Nevertheless, at present, for privacy reasons, no user data is saved in the system, consequently no data is present that needs aggregation in the ARIADNE Catalogue or Platform, and therefore needs to be encoded in AO-Cat or CIDOC CRM. In any case, the system has already been enhanced and equipped to be machine actionable and capable of producing semantic data on demand, should it become necessary in the future to save user data, share it and make it interoperable with other ARIADNE information.

The added value of the ARIADNE DMP Template compared to other existing templates, stands in the guidelines provided in support of the questions and the suggested answers based on the standards and operative workflows adopted in archaeology. This way, users have a better understanding of the processes and methodologies used, and may also consider possible alternatives to their research approach.

3.6 The Policy Wizard tool

Building on work done in PARTHENOS, ARIADNEplus further developed and updated the Policy Wizard.¹⁹ This online service summarises and explains the main principles of archaeological data management and their implementation. It aims to help archaeologists discover which data policy applies best to their particular data. As part of the ARIADNEplus project, the tool was first revived by updating the database behind it and by updating the code. The Policy Wizard tool has been designed with a user-friendly interface that displays the information on the selected policies by the chosen community and topic(s).

¹⁹ <https://www.parthenos-project.eu/portal/wizard>

4 Providing guidelines and support on repository creation and management

Task 3.3 has provided guidelines and supported partners willing to set up an archaeological data repository. UoY-ADS led the task, with SND and CNR-ISTI (NEMIS-Infra). Other partners advised on national/local opportunities.

When task 3.3 was first created, it was set to take the form of draft guidance to be produced towards the middle of the project (with a revised version planned for delivery at the end), linked to TNA from WP9. However, the COST Action Saving European Archaeology from the Digital Dark Age (SEADDA),²⁰ was funded concurrently with ARIADNEplus (partly as result of work during and recommendations coming out of ARIADNE). SEADDA has participants from 34 countries, including all countries represented by ARIADNEplus partners. ARIADNEplus and the ARIADNE Portal continued to develop the state-of-the-art for the aggregation of archaeological data, while SEADDA focused on the long-term trajectory of the data itself. It has expanded the capacity-building necessary for organisations, regions and countries to expand their participation in ARIADNEplus in a more equitable way through collaborative stewardship.

Task 3.3 was updated into deeper work and collaboration across four different working groups (WG), and the ability of ARIADNEplus partners to participate in SEADDA Short Term Scientific Missions for more intensive work. The four WGs are:

WG1. Stewardship of Archaeological Data

Objective: To bring together members with varying levels of experience to share their successes and challenges around the stewardship of archaeological data to create a sub-network.

WG2. Planning for Archiving

Objective: To identify the practical and technical issues surrounding the creation of an appropriate repository for archaeological data.

WG3. Preservation and Dissemination Best Practice

Objective: To understand current international best practice with regard to archiving and dissemination, and implementation by existing repositories.

WG4. Use and Re-use of Archaeological Data

Objective: To understand how to optimise archives and interfaces to maximise the use and re-use of archaeological data, and explore how archaeological archives can better respond to user needs, and ways to document and understand both quantitative and qualitative re-use.

Exploratory workshops took place in 2019-2020, and by 2021, 28 articles were published in a comprehensive, open access themed issue *Digital Archiving in Archaeology: The State of the Art* representing a wide range of countries, nations and regions on the current state of data stewardship in archaeology [Richards et al. 2021].

²⁰ <http://seadda.eu>

The 2021 survey mentioned in section 2 and discussed in more detail in [section 6](#), was conducted by ARIADNEplus with SEADDA WG3, and published as a deliverable report and an open access journal article.²¹

A workshop bringing together WG1 and WG4 took place in Braga, Portugal, in May 2022.²² The discussions included updates from the work of the first two years, along with the work before completion of the Action in September of 2023. One of the aims of SEADDA is to develop a European network of contacts, and determine which organisations are well placed to host data management and stewardship workshops within their countries. National workshops in national languages were held in Serbia, France, Portugal, and Turkey in 2022. Further workshops are planned for Ireland, Israel and Romania in 2023.

A second themed issue of *Digital Archiving in Archaeology: The State of the Art* will be published in 2023 with articles representing Croatia, Romania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Ireland, Cyprus, and Germany.

This will be followed by a synthetic publication on the state-of-the-art and advancing stewardship of archaeological data in Europe, based on the *Digital Archiving in Archaeology: The State of the Art* themed issues will be published in 2023.

A survey of qualitative analysis procedures and technologies to better understand re-use and barriers to re-use was finalised and circulated in Year 3 for GIS, 3D and radiocarbon dating use cases.

Participation in a sustainable resource for supporting repository management called Community Owned digital Preservation Tool Registry (COPTR) was also part of ARIADNEplus. COPTR is both a registry of preservation tools and a documentation platform for preservation workflows. In 2022, members participated in two COPTR hackathons focussed on 3D data and spatial data, and are considering a preservation workflow hackathon for established repositories of archaeological data.

Collaboration has continued in 2022 between DANS/ADS and the Swedish National Heritage Board as part of participation in the URDAR project, particularly around use of IntraSyS exports, which has joined up this work across the multiple approaches taken by ARIADNEplus partners separately.

In the autumn of 2021, the new DCCD (Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology) portal for tree-ring data was launched.²³ Together, the Dutch Cultural Heritage Agency (RCE) and DANS worked on this new portal for depositing, downloading and (inter)nationally disseminating tree-ring data. This international digital data library of tree-ring data contains measurements of tree-ring patterns (growth ring series) as well as their descriptive and interpretive metadata and research reports. By means of dendrochronological research the calendar year in which a tree was previously cut down can be determined. This allows wooden objects to be dated. In addition, more can be learned about development and use of landscapes. As a result, research reports and measurement series can be found about objects and sites from prehistory up to the present day. The archive contains data from European institutes. Each organisation displays its own collection of data related to archaeological sites, shipwrecks, buildings, furniture, paintings, sculptures and, for example, musical instruments. ARIADNEplus is now able to harvest this scientific data to integrate this with other archaeological data

²¹ Geser et al. "Data Management Policies and Practices of Digital Archaeological Repositories", <https://doi.org/10.11141/ia.59.2>; Hollander, H. (2022). "D3.2 Interim report on policies and strategies." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6380113>; see also Geser, "D2.1 Initial Report on Community Needs", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4916190>.

²² <https://www.seadda.eu/?p=1731>

²³ <https://dataverse.nl/dataverse/dccd>

and to show this via the ARIADNE portal. In November 2022, a DCCD symposium was held to present the results to a multidisciplinary group of researchers at the Cultural Heritage Agency (RCE) in Amersfoort. New guidelines for best practices and policies for dendrochronological research were presented.²⁴

In Italy, as part of the ARIADNEplus project, a digital infrastructure has been set up to collect and store data on archaeological research carried out under a ministerial concession, the D4GNA (Dataset for the National Geoportal for Archaeology), which is currently being released online. The aim is to make available to research directors a tool for uploading and sharing data collected in the field, which will enable them to share on the web in an open format an initial registry of the research, facilitating the exchange of information between insiders and other parties, both institutional and private, interested in consulting the data. The datasets are uploaded onto the portal according to the guidelines issued by the Ministry of Culture through the Central Institute for Archaeology, which validates their format and content, guaranteeing their quality, before they are published online. It is also planned that research data will be stored permanently, making it possible to consult documentation from previous years. D4GNA performs conversion to new formats during the ingest phase and enhances metadata and documentation. The ingest phase is also complemented by a data-level curation performed by the domain experts working as moderators of the publication process. D4GNA manages, and communicates to relevant stakeholders all rights (permissions, prohibitions, obligations) covering data and metadata deposit, storage, preservation, access, and use and put in place all the controls to ensure that they are applied and monitored. Moreover, business continuity and disaster recovery are ensured by the operational policies properly communicated to the stakeholders. D4GNA operates a data and metadata management system that maintains provenance information and ensures authenticity from deposition, through curation to the point of access. State of the art measures ensure that unintentional or unauthorised changes are promptly detected and corrective actions are put in place to ensure that data and metadata are recovered. Finally, D4GNA operates on reliable and stable core infrastructure that maximises service availability and reliability.

²⁴ Each downloadable from <https://www.sikb.nl/archeologie/publicaties-archeologie/download>.

5 Providing guidelines and support on repository quality control

Task 3.4 has provided guidelines and support to partners willing to accredit their repository and their data according to the most important accreditation systems presently leading to CoreTrustSeal, as well as to other systems in use in different EU countries. It attentively followed the evolution of policies on the matter and provide indications from the archaeological research perspective to international initiatives in the field, for example concerning restriction of access for security and privacy reasons, issues related to language use (multilinguality), or, on the other hand, the implication and an explanation of accreditation requirements when applied to repositories of archaeological data.

DANS-KNAW leads the task, with the support of UoY-ADS, MIBACT-ICCU, DGPC, and SND.

5.1 Certification support

This task gave support to partners willing to accredit and certify their repository, and provided recommendations to be used beyond the duration of ARIADNEplus. CoreTrustSeal certification²⁵ is the most widely used standard for trusted digital archives worldwide. By obtaining such a certification seal, the organisation makes clear that the sustainability and the reliability of the digital archive is guaranteed. In March 2021, together with the Dutch Digital Heritage Network (NDE), eight recommendations were extracted based on the practical experiences of ARIADNEplus partner institutions that went through all the steps of the certification process (e.g., the Swedish National Data Service (SND), the Archaeological Data Service (ADS), MIBACT-ICCU).²⁶

1. Start by reading the CoreTrustSeal Requirements and Extended Guidance. These documents provide a good overview of what might be expected per Requirement, including tips for documentation. Continue by zooming out from this detailed matter and consider for each Requirement how this can be applied to the practice of your digital archive.
2. Do not only collect evidence, but also ensure that this is published and accessible to everyone on your own website. It is better to have a clear and well-arranged story on a part of your website than to supply a huge list of documents.
3. Involve people from across the organisation to gather the information you need. Going through a certification process is a cross-departmental activity. A small team with specific knowledge can write the text for the submission.
4. Assume a reviewer knows nothing about your institute. Explain the context, organisation and infrastructure in a way that can also be understood by outsiders.
5. Usually you don't get the certificate in one go, so don't see this as a failure and do expectation management at the start of the process. In terms of planning, take into account several revision rounds which can take several months.
6. Look for inspiring examples of national and international institutes that have fulfilled certain requirements. All approved CoreTrustSeal applications are publicly available on the CoreTrustSeal website.
7. If you include 'Outsource partners' in your application, make it clear which requirements are fulfilled by the external partner and how this is recorded by contracts (e.g. a service level agreement).

²⁵ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

²⁶ https://wegwijzercertificering.nl/nl/8_tips_uit_de_praktijk (currently only in Dutch, with the current document serving as an English summary)

8. Realise that perfection is not the highest goal of a CoreTrustSeal certification process, but that there is a compliance level per Requirement. If things are still in the implementation phase, explain why this is the case and describe the work towards full implementation.

In June 2022, the DANS Data Station Archaeology was launched in The Netherlands. This newly created and domain-specific repository needs to obtain a CoreTrustSeal certification to guarantee long-term and secure storage of the archaeological collection according to the newest standards. The self-assessment has been submitted and is currently under review. Official assessment guidelines and protocols are part of the certification system archaeological organisations are obliged to follow according to the Dutch Heritage act. It is prescribed that information must be permanently stored in a certified e-depot for durable storage of digital data. ADS is also currently planning for the renewal of their CoreTrustSeal certification, scheduled for Spring 2023.

From January 2023, the requirements for CoreTrustSeal certification will slightly change. Mainly textual changes have been made to clarify what CoreTrustSeal is asking for. During the DANS Data Trail *Certificering met de nieuwe CoreTrustSeal Requirements*,²⁷ these changes were highlighted and explained (in Dutch). The webinar focussed on heritage institutions and can be viewed online and the slides are made available for downloading.

²⁷ DANS Data Trail: Certificering met de nieuwe CoreTrustSeal Requirements. 17 November 2022. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SfZIYqQ3vPY>; DANS has also participated in producing a series of English-language YouTube videos about the new requirements, available through the [CoreTrustSeal YouTube channel](#), [playlist 2023-2025 requirements](#).

6 Managing FAIRness of archaeological data and IPR

Task 3.5 was led by MiBACT-ICCU and assessed the impact of European and national regulations on data policies in archaeology, with the aim to make archaeological data compliant with the FAIR principles. The archaeological data treatment related to IPR issues is complex, both because of the multiplicity of contents that can be produced and for the presence of the different actors involved. In pursuing this objective, the task analysed the different restrictions imposed by legal regimes and the way archaeologists respond to them, how they are interpreted, and how they influence behaviour. Moreover, it identified good practices, specifically in relation to the legal protection of personal data, the protection of intellectual property rights and the use of licences or waivers to indicate the terms of re-use.

6.1 Survey

An online survey was carried out in 2021 as a collaboration between researchers responsible for Task 3.5 “Managing FAIRness of archaeological data and IPR” (Flavia Masssara, ICCU) and Task 2.2 “Reviewing the community needs and the market” (Guntram Geser, SRFG). The main purposes of the survey were to collect and analyse information for assessing current policies that determine access to and reuse of data held by digital archaeological repositories, and providing guidance and support needed to make the repositories and data FAIR.

The survey was addressed to directors, managers and curators of digital archaeological repositories (ARIADNEplus and SEADDA partners, and representatives of other repositories). A total of 60 responses were collected from repositories in 35 countries. The survey participants included 43 operative repositories and 17 repositories in the process of becoming operative, so the answers were meant to be both practical and inspirational. For seven repositories, two respondents each provided information. With 94 contacts having been directly invited, this means the survey had a response rate of 64%, although a few respondents did not answer all questions.

The survey represents a bottom-up approach by focusing on the actual data policies and practices of digital archaeological repositories. This allows an evaluation to what extent these conform to ideals of FAIR and open access data. A reality-check in this regard can enable heritage and research authorities, councils and other institutions to reinforce or put in place regulations that bring current repository policies and practices closer to the envisaged ideals. The survey results show that there is quite some room for improvement in this regard.

The methods and results of the survey were presented in detail in D3.2 and in the article *Data Management Policies and Practices of Digital Archaeological Repositories* [Geser et al. 2022].

The survey covered a range of topics and the survey questions were created to cover important aspects addressed by the FAIR Principles in ways that were easily answered by respondents without referring to the Principles directly. This included data deposition and curation, FAIRness and data access policies, and enabling open data access, for example by asking about the use of persistent identifiers, metadata richness, vocabularies, data discovery, and licensing. Data discovery included both repository search interfaces and external aggregation platforms. The main conclusions from the survey results and suggestions for activities of ARIADNEplus, SEADDA, and other initiatives were:

6.1.1 Repository support of FAIR data

- *(Meta)data identifiers*: 29 of the 60 repositories surveyed assign globally unique and persistent identifiers to deposited data, but for many more this would be beneficial. Initiatives for state-of-the-art repositories should provide advice on how to assign such identifiers.
- *Metadata richness*: The majority of repositories (47) are satisfied with the metadata they provide, which suggests no need for targeted support activities. However, in the responses to the question what would help most for improving data access, 34 repositories considered improvement of the quality of metadata. Hence this is still an important topic for advice on good practice.
- *Vocabulary support*: Most of the repositories use more than one vocabulary (39), often two (20) or three (17). Often, an own standardised vocabulary (35) and/or a national vocabulary (25) is being applied. However, quite a few of the repositories use less formalised means such as an own list of terms and/or keywords given by depositors (e.g., eight use only this, nine also use in addition an own standardised vocabulary). Therefore, advice on how to standardise vocabulary and/or align it with an international one (e.g., Getty AAT) would be beneficial.
- *Data discovery*: 24 repositories do not have a metadata search interface and 35 do not share metadata with external search platforms. The reasons for this would be worth investigating in order to advise on how metadata could be provided to data search platforms such as the ARIADNE portal.
- *Licence frameworks*: While 16 repositories have a very open approach regarding data re-use, 19 have a very restricted one and 17 repositories apply some restrictions. Advice on copyright clearance or why some restrictions should be reconsidered (e.g., no commercial use, no derivatives or other) may be helpful for increasing the potential of data re-use.

6.1.2 Enabling open data access

- *Support of open data policies*: a clear position of heritage authorities is needed; 39 repositories required regulations and 36 clear guidelines by the authorities. Other support is also needed, for example, 28 repositories considered training of repository staff to support new policies on open/FAIR data just as important.
- *Regulation of archaeological documentation*: 36 respondents said that there is a national legislation in their country that determines which documentation of archaeological investigations and interventions has to be provided to a repository, while 24 said there is no such legislation. Some perceived existing regulations as insufficient and often a lack of or an inappropriate repository was also mentioned. Thus, in many countries regulations for rich archaeological documentation and appropriate repositories for such documentation would be needed.
- *Directive (EU) 2019/1024 on public sector information*: when asked whether their repository is located in the European Union and falls under this Directive, 21 out of 46 respondents said “Yes”, 5 “No”, and 20 “Don’t know”. This suggests that more legal support for repositories is needed to understand whether the Directive also applies to them, and what the consequences are if this is the case.
- *Control of data access*: At 21 repositories data is only accessible for legitimate registered users and/or with permission granted. In addition, 15 repositories have such restrictions for some of the data, while 24 repositories have an open access approach (i.e., no registration is required). Reducing the barriers to data access would require mechanisms for not disclosing sensitive data and advice could be given on this topic.
- *Improving data access*: The repositories considered what would help them most for improving data access and often this included:
 - improving or replacing the existing data management system (30 respondents), - improving the quality of metadata (34),

- providing metadata to external search platforms/engines (27),
- using Linked Data to interlink own and other (meta)data (26).

Analysing separately the responses for repositories in preparation (17) and in operation (43) showed some specific needs. For example:

- Repositories in preparation that were satisfied with their data management and vocabulary wanted their data to be found by providing metadata to external search platforms and possibly interlink own and other (meta)data using the Linked Data approach.
- For some repositories in operation that were not satisfied with their data management system, the main reason appeared to be enabling better access to complex or high-volume data objects (e.g., 3D models, LiDAR data).
- Among the repositories in operation, one group primarily wanted to improve the metadata quality and to replace or align their own with other vocabulary, while another group wanted to provide metadata to external search platforms and possibly interlink own and other (meta)data using the Linked Data approach.

The results show that repositories could benefit greatly from advice and support in several areas, in particular, from the perspective of ARIADNEplus, regarding improvement of metadata, providing metadata to the ARIADNE catalogue and portal, and Linked Data.

6.1.3 Analysis of data access and reuse

Repositories also need advice and possibly support regarding collection and analysis of information about data access and re-use:

- Data access: 29 out of 56 respondents said that their repository does not collect and analyse data access figures, although this might allow identifying where access procedures and reporting on repository usage could be improved.
- Data re-use: No information about data re-use (e.g., references in publications and other sources) is being collected according to 47 of the 56 respondents, although re-use for new research and other purposes best demonstrates that funds for data preservation and access are well invested.

Finally, 24 of the 27 repositories which analyse data access reported that during the COVID-19 pandemic overall there was an increased access, reporting increases from 5% to over 100%, and this is encouraging for the open/FAIR data agenda. It seems likely that the COVID-19 crisis made archaeologists more aware of the importance of publicly shared data, data repositories and discovery and access services.

6.1.4 Proposals to support open data and reuse policies

Although knowledge and attention to FAIR data is increasingly widespread, many steps still have to be taken. In conclusion, after the survey feedback, some suggestions emerged to harmonise the different approaches adopted by different partners and countries:

- Clear guidelines and regulations from authorities are needed. This emerged as the most important help the repositories could receive to support open data access and reuse policies.
- Increasing awareness and knowledge by all involved parties is necessary to overcome users' concerns about depositing open and reusable data, mainly relating to open licensing and that data might be misused. It is also important they understand they work for the general public.
- More trained staff (to support both researchers and repository staff) is also required to support new policies.

These attitudes could help support repositories in open data access and reuse policies by avoiding misinterpretation of the application of FAIR data, as Dunning et al. 2017, state in their research:

"The 15 facets of the FAIR principles are all short sentences. Their brevity gives the impression that they are all items that can be checked off. However, our analysis shows that the FAIR principles are much trickier than this".

The article in which the results were published [Geser et al. 2022] supplements the country-by-country state of the art reviews published in 2021 [Richards et al. 2021] and makes suggestions for initiatives aimed to support FAIR data, data policies, and to improve data access.

7 Training on FAIR Data Management

Task 3.6 was led by DANS-KNAW and organised workshops on FAIR data management in years 2 and 4. Training resources were provided via an online Training Hub. Webinars were organised.

The workshops were originally envisioned as short and intense, spanning three days with additional visits to a relevant innovative (Dutch) research or data facility. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic safety limitations on organising in-person meetings, the planned 3-day year-2 event in March 2020 had to be restructured as a one-day virtual meeting. It consisted of a series of lectures in the morning as well as a *SEADDA WG3 meeting* with discussions on the themes of FAIR Data Management and Trust Concepts and Standards in the afternoon. A total of 42 participants joined the sessions, although not all of them were there for the entire meeting.

As an alternative to in-person workshops and seminars, the online **Training Hub** was set up.²⁸ It provides training resources for archaeological researchers and practitioners. A number of key topics, chosen based on feedback from the User Needs Survey, are covered through online resources, training workshops and webcasts. In addition, links are provided to external sources that may be of interest.

Figure 6. Start screen of the ARIADNEplus-related DANS Data Trail.

In March 2022 a successful (online) DANS Data Trail Workshop was held: *Data Management Tools for Archaeologists – How can the European ARIADNEplus Project help you?*²⁹ In the ARIADNEplus project, online tools were developed to assist archaeologists who want to (or are obliged to) make a data management plan including a protocol for Archaeological Data Management, a standard Data Management Plan (DMP) for archaeological research based on the principle of “comply or explain” and a guidance document for archaeological Data Management with lots of recommendations and good practices. The workshop introduced the tools to archaeologists and data professionals, provided the opportunity to try them out, and collected feedback on their functionality and usability (Fig.6).

²⁸ <https://training.ariadne-infrastructure.eu>

²⁹ DANS Data Trail: Data management tools for archaeologists. 29 March 2022. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KpvqxHbz594>.

In April 2022, DANS organised a FAIR workshop to highlight the results from the FAIRsFAIR project³⁰ *Explore new tools for your FAIR toolkit*, which is visible online.³¹ A FAIR Teaching handbook and Good Practices report can be downloaded [Garbuglia et al. 2021]. The F-UJI tool for assessing the FAIRness of data can be used to bring data stewardship into practice and the training and education manual helps to support staff of higher education institutions integrating FAIR and Research Data Management related content in their teaching and curricula. ARIADNEplus partners, like ADS as described below, can use these tools to start implementing a data management workflow to improve the FAIR quality of their data.

In relation to certification guidance (Task 3.4), DANS organised another DANS Data Trail on Certification for heritage institutions using the new CoreTrustSeal requirements.³²

A well-attended *CARARE webinar* was held in May 2022: *Step by Step, one travels FAIR*. Hella Hollander of DANS and Kathryn Cassidy of the Digital repository of Ireland showed examples of some of the ways in which cultural heritage datasets are becoming FAIR.

The *second SEADDA WG3 workshop* planned for year 4 was held in The Hague in June 2022. It was a very productive and stimulating meeting as this was one of the first face-to-face meetings after a very long time. An international group of researchers (14 in total) spoke about the *Future challenges and trends in the archaeological and digital domains*. The first topic was an example of how to implement a data management workflow based on FAIR criteria as a repository by the Archaeology Data Service (ADS). For this *FAIR audit* the F-UJI tool - a tool to assess FAIRness of data developed in the now finished FAIRsFAIR project led by DANS³³ - was used and feedback was given about the usability of the tool. In the follow-up FAIR IMPACT project the F-UJI tool will be improved. On the website of the ADS is specified how the ADS ensures compliance with all aspects of FAIR for each of the FAIR principles.³⁴ For future work, it would be very interesting to look at options for infrastructures by expanding on CIDOC-CRM mappings of metadata from different partners. The workshop continued with the next topic by sharing experiences and knowledge about setting up a repository. Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) presented the new *Dutch Data Station Archaeology* which was launched in June 2022.³⁵ A domain repository for cultural heritage data with an archaeological-specific metadata block and the use of archaeological thesauri. Challenges regarding interoperability were discussed: How to integrate different community-specific standards so the user can query the data in a broader perspective? User requirements, the data management process, architecture and future vision of the Data Station Archaeology were presented and discussed. During the workshop, round table discussions were held to *compare and contrast internal workflows and discuss common, shared archiving issues*. There was a discussion about the decision tree of DANS, ADS, and SND (Swedish National Data Service) regarding certain types of data (e.g. ACCESS, images, GIS). Paul Wheatly of the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) presented the *COPTR*³⁶ *Signpost for preservation tools*. During the

³⁰ <https://www.fairsfair.eu>

³¹ DANS Data Trail: Explore new tools for your FAIR toolkit. 21 April 2022. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iA7UudLpWDI&list=PLGCrt17ZLM3SgN85LPUB-gYFbB_gXVpN&index=3; <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/news/highlights-from-the-data-trail-on-new-fair-tools/>.

³² DANS Data Trail: Certificering voor erfgoedinstellingen met de nieuwe CoreTrustSeal requirements. 17 November 2022. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SfZlYqQ3vPY&list=PLGCrt17ZLM3SgN85LPUB-gYFbB_gXVpN&index=1

³³ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/f-uji-automated-fair-data-assessment-tool>

³⁴ <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/about/adsFAIR.xhtml>

³⁵ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/data-stations/archaeology/>

³⁶ https://coptr.digipres.org/index.php/Main_Page

workshop it was agreed that we would like to try to get documentation workflows in COPTR regarding assessing information (quality), deaccessioning data and (tool specific) ways of dealing with Access.³⁷

At the end of August 2022, at the *ARIADNEplus meeting* in Budapest prior to the European Archaeological Conference EAA, the following presentations were given by DANS to the partners attending: Policies and good practices for FAIR data management (ARIADNE) and Preservation and dissemination best practice (SEADDA). At the *EAA conference, a joint ARIADNEplus and SEADDA session* was held addressing the reuse of archaeological data: *FAIRly Front-loading the Archive: Moving beyond Findable, Accessible and Interoperable to Reuse of Archaeological Data*.

An example of making structured data reusable is the research of Dr. Alex Brandsen. Within the EXALT project (Excavating Archaeological Literature) a multilingual search engine for archaeological texts is developed. *AGNES* is a tool working like Google for archaeological reports.³⁸ Thousands of grey literature reports can be searched through for specific topics or words. A seminar (a hybrid meeting) at DANS was organised in September 2022: *Can Bert dig it? Named Entity Recognition*. Artificial Intelligence is used to enable new discoveries about the human past.

³⁷ Workflows can also be described in COPTR => Community Owned Workflows (COW). See also [https://coptr.digipres.org/index.php/Further information about workflows](https://coptr.digipres.org/index.php/Further%20information%20about%20workflows).

³⁸ <http://agnesearch.nl/>

Conclusions

As described in this final report on Policies and Good Practices for FAIR Archaeological Data Management, focused and dedicated support has established structured policies and strategies for the creation of archaeological data of high quality. A standardised and online tool offers a Data Management Plan for archaeologists which helps researchers to conduct their research following standard quality criteria. Researchers can save a lot of time when preparing a Data Management Plan, since a motivation is only required when deviating from the standard reply, which the Domain Protocol for Archaeological Data Management offers as pre-formulated statements. A related Guide for Archaeological Data Management Planning helps users in their work to find good practices in archaeological data management.

ARIADNEplus has focused on implementing European policies related to FAIR data. Workshops, webinars, symposia and hackathons took place and scientific articles on data management policies and practices of digital archaeological repositories were published to define and spread guidelines to good practices. Training and training materials have been produced and published and an online Training Hub was set up on the ARIADNEplus website.

Experiences were shared from partners with already certified repositories to partners willing to set up an archaeological data repository. Knowledge exchange took place and the explanation of and training on accreditation requirements of archaeological repositories supported partners in their process to certify their repository and provided recommendations to be used beyond the duration of ARIADNEplus.

The provided guidelines for the FAIRification of open data together with the automated aggregation process pipeline of ARIADNEplus played a major role in fostering open science within the archaeological community. Preparations took place to introduce ARIADNEplus to EOSC by informing the EOSC community about the FAIRness of archaeological data based on the work undertaken by ARIADNEplus.

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